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PHTHALONITRILE MODIFIED MULTI-HYDROXYL PHENOLIC: SYNTHESIS, CURING AND PROPERTIES

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In order to improve the processability and thermal stability of addition-curable phenolic resin, multi-hydroxyl phenolic with different phthalonitrile substitution degree was prepared. The chemical structure, curing behaviour, processability and thermal stability were studied. The curing temperature of HPPh2 was 259 °C while that of LPPh2 was 338 °C, as the result of different residual hydroxyl group contents. The rheological tests demonstrated that the processing window of LPPh2 was as wide as 155 °C while that of HPPh2 was only 75 °C. TG tests showed that the char yield at 800 °C of LPPh2 was as high as 76% due to the low residual hydroxyl contents after curing. The correlation between the phthalonitrile contents, hydroxyl contents and the properties of the resin was established, which is meaningful for the molecular design.

Reaction Scheme

Chemical Structure

Sample	O/C
LPh	0.14
HPh	0.22

Properties

Curing behaviour

Processability

Thermal stability